

Foldable/Unfoldable Curved Tensegrity Systems by Finite Mechanism Activation

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to present a complete design study of foldable/unfoldable curved tensegrity systems with all the steps involved: generation of the curved tensegrity lattice, introduction of finite mechanisms, structure analysis and folding/unfolding. Three criteria are required to introduce the finite mechanisms and self stress saving throughout the folding procedure. The new foldable/unfoldable tensegrity configurations which respect these criteria are classified and illustrated according to three parameters: direction of truss beam, surface's mean curvatures and direction of articulation axes. Several configurations are then developed.

INTRODUCTION

The foldable/unfoldable study of tensegrity systems with different geometry describes the relationship between form, self-stress and finite mechanisms. The geometry of the systems and the state of self-stress depend on the movability of the elements during the folding process. In tensegrity systems these obvious relationships become increasingly complex when adding the aspects of physical model, manufacture and function.

Double curved tensegrity systems may create efficient structures if developed with form and structure, function and economy in mind. However, not every form is required. Double curved surfaces alone cannot guarantee an executable design which satisfies the folding process requirements (geometrical and kinematical constraints) [1]. This research has to make foldable/unfoldable double curved tensegrity grid more accessible and apply the following aspects:

- Foldable/unfoldable tensegrity systems without having to remove completely the self-stress.
- Apply an approach on several structural configurations, in particular, on double-curved tensegrity grids.

Figure 1: Double layer tensegrity grid

PROBLEM AND AIMS

The first problem in the design of tensegrity structures is finding a self-stress equilibrium configuration throughout the folding process. This is an additional step in comparison with traditional foldable/unfoldable tensegrity [2]. However, the crucial design step is the creation of mechanisms that enable reliable folding/unfolding.

In the field of deployable structures a paper has recently appeared on folding tensegrity systems (lattice plane (Figure 1)) which keep self-stress throughout the folding process [3]. This study of that fundamental folding characteristics has enabled us generalize this process to other tensegrity grids with total curvature identically zero, positive and negative total curvature.

Concerning deployability, the second aim of the tensegrity concept is the folding process without having to remove completely the self-stress: the process is then dependant upon the intrinsic geometrical and foldable characteristics of the structure.

CONFIGURATION TYPOLOGIES

The multiplicity parameters whose can take part in this study cause enormous quantity that it is impossible to consider here than a few category, mainly the repetitive typologies. We examine the general principle effects that agree all spatiality: order, repetitively, diversity, proportion, density, orientation, etc...

The new configuration tensegrity lattices, which belong to the same typology (2V spacer), are filed according to three geometrical parameters. Each of these parameters consists also a sub-parameters whose the variations cause an infinity configurations. To describe these last, we establish the following parameters:

1. Direction of truss frame

- The systems whose the frames are parallels.
- The systems whose the frames converge in one or several points.

2. Surface's mean curvatures

- Surfaces with total curvature identically zero
- Surfaces with positive total curvature
- Surfaces with negative total curvature

3. Direction of articulation axes

- The systems whose the articulation axes are parallels
- The systems whose the articulation axes converge in one point.

Therefore, to choose a list for every configuration, every description system constitutes an explication for the geometrical constraints that allow a complete foldable/unfoldable (in the resulting position, all elements are mapped on the folding plane.) and different configurations; initial, middle and final position.

We focus our research for these cases only on configurations which have parallel frames and articulation axes and surface with total curvature identically zero or positive or negative total curvature. These parameters allow us to detect four different configurations:

- a) Planar tensegrity lattice.
- b) Double curvature tensegrity lattice I (surface with total curvature identically zero).
- c) Double curvature tensegrity lattice II (surface with positive total curvature).
- d) Double curvature tensegrity lattice III (surface with negative total curvature).

PLANAR TENSEGRITY LATTICE

This configuration have been illustrated and established in our previous publication appeared in IASS journal [3]. The constitutive modules are distributed according to a regular grid (Figure 2). For having configuration completely mapped on vertical plan, the elementary module can exist in varying shape but he has to respect the following geometrical conditions (Figure 2b):

- The vertical axes AA', BB', CC' and DD' are parallels
- The faces AA'BB' and CC'DD' are parallels and equal
- The faces AA'CC' and BB'DD' are parallels and equal

This elementary observation leads to tow finite mechanisms but we are interested only in one kind. The horizontal mechanism is a movement by "shear action", keeping horizontal the quadrangular face A'B'C'D'.

Figure 2: (a) Three-dimensional regular modules. (b) Horizontal finite mechanism (shear force)

The target folding plane is defined by the square AA'BB' (Figure 2b). All the lateral faces are not distorted in this displacement (if keeping self-stress).

Kinematically, the system illustrated in the Figure 3 contains numerous finite mechanisms whose direction varies in according with the horizontal plane. One of these finite mechanisms can act on a vertical folding plane, which corresponds to one of four vertical edges of the grid. The faces which are initially parallel to the folding plane get closer and closer together, following a zigzag path. In the folding position, all modules are mapped on the folding plane (Figure 4b).

This folding method leads to the development of a folding method applied to a curved grid using the same procedure. The new curved grid has of course a consequence on the resulting position, simultaneously on the number and the value of self-stress.

Figure 3: 9 basic cubic module assembly, (a) unfolded configuration, (b) intermediary configuration, (c) folded configuration

Figure 4: Folding of a real physical model by flattening the truss beams

DOUBLE CURVATURE TENSEGRITY LATTICE I (SURFACE WITH TOTAL CURVATURE IDENTICALLY ZERO)

The first problem is adopting a method which allows generating a new configuration passing from flatten to curvature lattice. The second obstacle in the design of curvature tensegrity lattice is finding a self-stress equilibrium configuration. Several methods are available, but a single method suitable for general problems. This method isn't apt without preserving all necessary geometrical constraints. Here, an approach, involving an orthogonal projection method, is proposed.

For a double curvature tensegrity lattice, this procedure is illustrated in the Figure 5a. The process consists projecting a flatten grid which is illustrated in the precede paragraph on a geometry desired, surface with total curvature identically zero (cylinder) (Figure 5). To preserve the foldable compatibility in this case, the direction of projection has to follow the direction of articulation axes. In like case, that projection incurs a new generation which respects a number of limits. Thus, the generation process gets the following steps:

- Defining the desired geometry (general form, the size, curvature radius, etc...) knowing that he has to accord with the original geometry.
- Appearing the intersection points between the projection axes and desired geometry
- Folding/unfolding the new geometry according the mechanisms which are linked to the main orthogonal directions of the grid.

Figure 5: Orthogonal projection method for double curved tensegrity grid

Finally, the obtained geometry which is based on a simple pavement has a different length of cables and struts comparing with mother geometry. But, the projection principle has preserved the direction and the number of finite mechanisms (Figure 5b).

To fold the new system, the method consists in flattening the parallel modules on the flatten plane. The vertical edges of the parallel faces are the rotation axes. A force is applied on external joint in the foldable direction in order to activate a shear mechanism, the system is reticulated and the degrees of freedom are fixed for half of the system Figure 6a. During this shear process all lateral faces move following a zigzag path. The result of the virtual simulation of the mechanism is given in the Figure 6d.

Figure 6: Foldable double-curved tensegrity grid process (surface with total curvature identically zero)

DOUBLE CURVATURE TENSEGRITY LATTICE II (SURFACE WITH POSITIVE TOTAL CURVATURE)

The configuration considered here is illustrated in the Figure 7a. The method considered has been established in the proceed paragraph. Starting from mother module, the configuration desired is formed by orthogonal projection on a surface with positive total curvature. The direction of projection should be parallel to articulation axes of mother module.

The intersection of four projection lines with the surfaces defines a module whose the typology is identical than the mother elementary module. Cinematically, this new module has also horizontal finite mechanisms. Geometrically, the new geometry of the system is characterized by the direction of projection and the radius of the surfaces. These are the parameters of the evolution. Mechanically, in the initial configuration (grid plane), the system has one or more states of self stress (the number of state of self stress is up to the typology of the system, geometry, fixed nods,...). But, the new configuration has different states of self stress which interfere the geometry once time again.

Figure 7: Orthogonal projection method for double-curved tensegrity grid (with positive total curvature)

The juxtaposition of several new modules, following a direction, gives a sector whose the geometrical compatibility allows a zigzag path to be mapped on a one of two vertical plans. The folding methods described in the preceding papers lead to the development of a folding method applied to a curved grid. The folding process consists to apply actions, which are opposite to a folding plane, until the all constitute modules are mapped on a folding plane Figure 8.

Figure 8: Foldable double-curved tensegrity grid process (surface with positive total curvature)

DOUBLE CURVATURE TENSEGRITY LATTICE III (SURFACE WITH NEGATIVE TOTAL CURVATURE)

To generate a foldable/unfoldable tensegrity system whose the double layers forms two parallel surfaces with negative total curvature, we proceed according to the method established in the precede paragraph. The geometric configuration created in Figure 9 is a grid generated by a orthogonal projection of the same flatten grid. Since the grid is made up with the same principle, the folding process, as illustrated before, should be activated by shear forces. This method is also a folding on a vertical folding plane, convex or concave beams move following a zigzag path (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Orthogonal projection method for double-curved tensegrity grid (with negative total curvature)

Figure 10: Foldable double-curved tensegrity grid process (surface with positive total curvature)

FOLDABLE/UNFOLDABLE DOUBLE CURVED TENSEGRITY LATTICE ANALYSIS

Four tensegrity grids, one flatten grid and three with double curved grid were examined (Figure 11). In the last paper [3], the first grid was described his structural behavior during the folding process. However, this part leads to describe the evolution of mechanical behavior of the missed grids. For this aim, we use a numeric simulation called tensegrity2000 (developed in Laboratoire de Mécanique et Génie Civil).

Figure 11: computer modeling of four tensegrity grids, (a) grid plane, (b) cylindrical grid, (c) spherical grid, (d) parabolic-hyperbolic grid

Each system is made of 12 struts and 28 cables according to the typology of 2V spacer (Figure 11). When the grids were self-stressed, a force is applied on a peripheral joint for each system. This force must be parallel to folding plane in order to activate a shear mechanism. Some other nodes are fixed to establish the folding plane in a stable position. During the folding process, closer examination revealed that the number of states of self-stress is not modified, but its level is alerted. The four systems, which were studied, could be folded in a satisfactory way. However, high local stresses were induced at the vertical cables. This revelation significantly leads that the internal forces haven't been canceled for all of the elements, displacement of the nodes are also computed (Figure 12).

CONCLUSION

These foldable/unfoldable systems of tensegrity with different geometry describe the relationship between form, self-stress and finite mechanisms. The geometry of the systems and the state of self-stress depend on the movability of the elements during the folding process. In tensegrity systems these obvious relationships become increasingly complex when adding the aspects of physical model, manufacture and function.

To synthesize this paper, we have established a new configurations, a wide range of possibilities for folding double curved (identically zero, negative and positive) tensegrity system, where during the folding process, the tensegrity systems remains in a state of self-stress. The parameters' diversity is very large, as good as the preliminary results regarding their mechanical behavior, the evolution of the self-stress and the finite mechanisms.

Figure 12: Variations in the degree of self-stress throughout the folding process, (a) according to grid plane, (b) according to cylindrical grid, (c) spherical grid, (d) Parabolic-Hyperbolical grid.

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